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Research on breast cancer induced chronic conditions
supported by causal analysis of multi-source data

D1.2 – REBECCA co-creation methodology and plan

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¹ Please use a new number for each new version of the deliverable. Use "0.#" for Draft and Peer-Reviewed. "x.#" for Submitted and Approved", where x>=1. Add the date when this version was issued and list the items that have been added or changed.

² A deliverable can be in one of these stages: Draft, Peer-Reviewed, Submitted and Approved.

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

BCP	Breast Cancer Patients
BCS	Breast Cancer Survivors
cApp	Companion app
CDC	Centers for Disease Control and Prevention
CRF	Case Report Form
ECFR	Electronic Case File Repository
EHR	Electronic Health Record
mHealth	mobile Health
pApp	Patient app
Pol	Point of Interest
QoL	Quality of Life
REDCap	Research Electronic Data Capture
SUS	System Usability Scale
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
UEQ	User Experience Questionnaire
WCRF	World Cancer Research Fund
WHO	World Health Organization

Executive Summary

Executive summary (updated, for version 2.0)

This document is the updated version of deliverable D1.2 at M39, incorporating new activities that were not included in the initial planning. These updates are highlighted in the newly added Section 4.

While both the validation of the REBECCA system and the cApp co-creation were initially planned, their specific methodologies had not been determined. The cApp co-creation followed an iterative process, integrating feedback from clinical experts before being refined through workshops with Amazona members, KI, and AUTH. Similarly, in June 2023, a validation study was conducted to assess the functionality and accuracy of the GPS in identifying Points of Interest (Pols), ensure proper data collection through the app and wearable devices, and refine the process based on participant feedback before the intervention studies.

In addition to these planned but undefined in methodology activities, three additional co-creation initiatives were introduced: a meeting with the Norwegian Cancer Society, the integration of positive event reporting categories into the pApp, and the feasibility study. The Norwegian Cancer Society organized a meeting with 30 of its members to discuss the ongoing REBECCA study at SUH. The addition of positive event reporting in the pApp was a patient-driven initiative, with KI leading an internal process that culminated in focused discussions with Amazonas to finalize the annotation options. Lastly, the feasibility study has recently begun, incorporating new features and app updates to evaluate BCS acceptance, engagement, and usage of the REBECCA system in real-world settings. A secondary aim is to assess potential improvements in QoL through personalized lifestyle consultations. The results of these activities will be documented in D1.4.

Executive summary (original, for version 1.0)

This document outlines the co-creation methodology, plan, and processes for the REBECCA project, designed to foster meaningful collaboration among patients, healthcare professionals, technical teams, and stakeholders. The methodology ensures the development of a user-centred platform, underpinned by a flexible evaluation framework that will evolve throughout the project lifecycle. The document serves as a live resource, with updates planned for milestones M9 (v1.0) and M39 (v2.0).

The evaluation framework integrates three core components: an adapted version of the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), the System Usability Scale (SUS), and the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ). The TAM adaptation specifically incorporates dimensions such as Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Security, and Perceived Trust, tailored to the REBECCA system's objectives. SUS and UEQ questionnaires collectively assess user perceptions of the app's utility, usability, and overall user experience

Co-creation activities based on this framework involve engaging users and stakeholders through focus groups to assess user preferences, a large-scale survey collected broader data on user requirements, workshops, and testing/co-designing the app. Collaborative workshops and clinical site meetings brought together healthcare professionals and technical teams to develop behavioural indicators for cancer-related fatigue and osteoporosis and one more meeting is scheduled for March to discuss relevant indicators to peripheral neuropathy. A pilot testing scheduled for April 2022 will provide insights into the app's usability and functionality, enabling refinements before full implementation. Additionally, to further evaluate the app's reliability and effectiveness for real-world use, a system validation is planned for spring 2023. Finally, the development of a standardized advisory guide will ensure consistent and personalized lifestyle counselling for BCS across all clinical sites.

The REBECCA project's co-creation methodology is designed to be participatory, iterative, and evidence-based, ensuring that the resulting platform is both effective and user-friendly. By engaging a wide range of stakeholders and leveraging structured evaluation tools, the project aims to enhance the quality of life (QoL) for breast cancer survivors (BCS) and provide actionable resources for healthcare professionals.

1 Introduction

This deliverable outlines the co-creation methodology and plan that will be implemented within the REBECCA project. The purpose of this document is to provide a comprehensive overview of the frameworks, processes, strategies, and activities involved in the co-creation efforts that have been carried out and are planned throughout the project's lifecycle. Co-creation plays a pivotal role in ensuring that the REBECCA system is developed in a way that effectively addresses the needs and perspectives of its key participants, including patients, healthcare professionals, the technical team, and other relevant parties.

1.1 Intended audience and reading suggestions

The intended audience for this document includes the REBECCA project development teams, representatives of the project's end-users within the consortium, and stakeholders with backgrounds in clinical research, technology, medicine, or policy. Readers are encouraged to follow a sequential reading approach through the chapters.

1.2 Methodology

Co-creation activities have been designed to involve all relevant parties to the project at every stage of development, ensuring that their insights and expertise contribute to the refinement of the system and its components. These activities, designed based on the TAM framework, include focus groups, a large-scale survey, expert workshops, clinical site meetings, testing of the app, and user experience evaluations through structured tools. The iterative nature of these processes allows for ongoing adjustments and improvements based on user feedback, ensuring that the system is aligned with the needs of all involved parties and maximizes its potential to improve patient outcomes.

1.3 Organization of the document

The updated document is structured into three main sections: **evaluation framework** (Section 2), the **co-creation activities** (Section 3) and the **updates and additions to co-creation activities at M39** (Section 4). Section 2 provides a description of the methodology and tools that will be employed to assess the usability, user experience, and acceptance of the REBECCA system. Section 3 outlines both the completed and planned co-creation efforts aimed at actively involving key stakeholders in the development process. Sections 2 and 3 were developed during the first version of the document (M9) and are designed to offer a comprehensive understanding of the

processes guiding the project's development, with an emphasis on user-centred design and continuous improvement. Then, Section 4, which was added for the second version of the document (M39), provides an overview of both the planned activities and those conducted up to M39 that were not initially included in the co-creation activity plan.

2 Evaluation framework

To ensure the development of a robust and user-centred platform, the REBECCA project will incorporate a continuous evaluation framework throughout its lifecycle. This framework is crucial for fostering meaningful engagement with patients, healthcare professionals, and stakeholders, offering a systematic approach to assess, refine, and validate the project's outputs. A key element of this approach is the adoption of a flexible and adaptive evaluation framework that evolves to meet the project's needs.

The project's evaluation strategy is a combination of three components: (i) an adapted version with items from the Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), combined with two widely used technology assessment questionnaires, namely (ii) the System Usability Scale (SUS) and (iii) the User Experience Questionnaire (UEQ). TAM provides insights into users' perceptions of the platform's ease of use and utility, while SUS and UEQ will serve as key instruments for assessing usability and user satisfaction across various stages of the project. In the following section, further details on the evaluation framework are provided.

2.1 Technology Acceptance Model

The evaluation of the REBECCA system's acceptance, including its functionality, usability, and user satisfaction, will be conducted through project-specific evaluation forms. These forms will be designed to capture valuable feedback from end-users. The creation of these evaluation tools is grounded in the TAM, a widely recognized framework for understanding user adoption of new technologies, originally developed by Fred Davis in the 1980s.

TAM emerged from research in information systems and has since become a foundational model for analysing how individuals decide to adopt new technologies. Initially conceptualized by Fred Davis in 1986 and further developed in collaboration with Richard Bagozzi in 1989, TAM explores the factors that influence technology acceptance³. Its relevance extends to evaluating systems like REBECCA, as it focuses on understanding the adoption of innovative technology within existing workflows.

The core principles of TAM emphasize two key factors: perceived usefulness (PU) and perceived ease of use (PEOU). PU refers to the extent to which users believe a technology will enhance their performance or provide practical benefits, while PEOU

³ Marangunić N, Granić A. Technology acceptance model: a literature review from 1986 to 2013. *Universal access in the information society*. 2015 Mar;14:81-95.

reflects the users' perception of how simple the technology is to use. These factors influence users' intentions to adopt and ultimately use the technology. Over time, TAM has been adapted and applied across various domains, including health, where it has been used to evaluate technologies like electronic health records, wearable devices, and mobile health applications for both patients and healthcare providers⁴.

To meet the specific needs of the REBECCA project, a modified version of TAM⁵, incorporating additional dimensions tailored to the system's objectives, will be used (Figure 1). This adaptation includes factors such as Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, Perceived Security, and Perceived Trust. These elements were selected to provide a comprehensive evaluation of the perspectives of both medical experts and patients regarding the REBECCA system.

In this adapted framework, "**Perceived Usefulness**" assesses how effectively the REBECCA system supports users in achieving their goals, such as improving QoL for patients, enhancing decision-making for medical experts, and optimizing treatment outcomes for both groups. "**Perceived Ease of Use**" evaluates the system's user-friendliness, and the effort required to operate it, a critical factor for its widespread adoption. "**Perceived Security**" examines users' confidence in the system's ability to protect sensitive information and maintain privacy which is a crucial consideration in medical technology. Finally, "**Perceived Trust**" measures the users' confidence in the system's reliability, integrity, and ability to meet its stated objectives. Trust plays a vital role in fostering positive user experiences and encouraging long-term engagement with the system.

⁴ AlQudah AA, Al-Emran M, Shaalan K. Technology acceptance in healthcare: A systematic review. *Applied Sciences*. 2021 Nov 9;11(22):10537.

⁵ Alloghani M, Hussain A, Al-Jumeily D, Abuelma'atti O. Technology Acceptance Model for the Use of M-Health Services among health related users in UAE. In 2015 International Conference on Developments of E-Systems Engineering (DeSE) 2015 Dec 13 (pp. 213-217). IEEE.

Figure 1. Modified Technology Acceptance Model

2.2 The System Usability Scale

Originally created to evaluate the usability of software and system interfaces, the SUS is a quick and reliable tool for gathering user feedback on various platforms. Consisting of ten questions, it balances positive and negative statements to produce a usability score between 0 and 100⁶. Its adaptability across different languages and cultural settings has made it an essential resource in evaluating usability in global contexts, spanning sectors such as healthcare, education, and e-commerce. The Swedish System Usability Scale and aggregated scores are shown in Figure 2.

⁶ Lewis JR. The system usability scale: past, present, and future. *International Journal of Human-Computer Interaction*. 2018 Jul 3;34(7):577-90.

Figure 2. Examples of the System Usability Scale in Swedish, as well as a representation of the outcome score representation, aggregated across all 10 evaluation items.

In healthcare, SUS has been widely used to assess the usability of health technologies, including electronic health record (EHR) systems, mobile health (mHealth) interventions, and healthcare applications aimed at prevention or treatment. It provides a standardized measure of user satisfaction and ease of use. Moreover, SUS has proven effective in evaluating wearable health devices and medical equipment, supporting the iterative design and enhancement of these technologies to better meet user needs.

2.3 The User Experience Questionnaire

The UEQ⁷ is a standardized tool designed to assess the user experience of interactive products. Developed in 2005, the UEQ evaluates six distinct quality aspects of a product: **Attractiveness**, **Perspicuity**, **Efficiency**, **Dependability**, **Stimulation**, and **Novelty**. Its construction was based on a data-driven approach to ensure the relevance of each scale, with the final version consisting of 26 items (Figure 3). These items were selected from a larger initial pool using principal component analysis, and the questionnaire has since been standardized in over 30 languages, including all those relevant to the REBECCA project.

⁷ <https://www.ueq-online.org/>

Figure 3. Examples of the User Experience Questionnaire in English and Spanish, along with an illustration of aggregated results across the six outcome scales.

In the healthcare domain, the UEQ has proven valuable for understanding user experiences with various digital health solutions. It has been used to evaluate EHRs, assessing their impact on user satisfaction and workflow efficiency for both patients and healthcare professionals⁴. Additionally, the UEQ has been applied to mHealth apps and wearable devices, providing insights into usability, visual design, and the perceived effectiveness of health-related interventions. Beyond these applications, it has also been used to assess health information websites and online health communities, contributing to the design and optimization of digital platforms aimed at health information dissemination and patient support.

3 Co-creation activities

This section focuses on the co-creation activities planned within the REBECCA project. These activities are, and will be, designed based on the principles outlined in the previously described evaluation framework. This approach aims to ensure meaningful engagement with a diverse group of participants including patients, healthcare professionals, the technical team, and other stakeholders, and thereby integrating a broad range of perspectives into the system's development process. The timeline of the co-creation activities that have already been conducted since the beginning of the project followed by the co-creation activities planned until M39, are presented in Figure 4.

Figure 4. Timeline of co-creation activities

3.1 System co-creation through BCP focus groups

The aim of the co-creation workshop, conducted in the form of focus groups, was to gather valuable insights into the BCP needs and preferences. The workshop took place between June 2nd and 4th, 2021 and was organized and hosted by the breast cancer society Amazona in Stockholm, with support from KI. The workshop was conducted online and recorded via the online video conferencing software Zoom (Zoom Video Communications, California, USA).

The focus group discussions explored participants' experiences with technology, opinions on the companion app, comfort with sharing personal data, and perceptions of the system's value, alongside feedback to refine the study questionnaire. The focus group topic guides can be found in A.1.

In addition, two narrative scenarios outlining use-cases were presented to better understand how BCPs viewed the potential use and value of the system. The first scenario, "System use in everyday life of a BCP," described interactions with the dedicated smartphone application, the wearable device, and a browser plugin,

alongside a secondary companion app. It highlighted routines and key functionalities to help participants identify priorities, constraints, and opportunities for improvement. The second scenario, "System use during a clinical meeting of a BCP and their doctor," illustrated how the system could support doctors in gaining a detailed view of a patient's condition before meetings, showcasing various levels of information detail. The entire scenarios are given in the Appendix of D1.1.

Women of all ages who had been diagnosed with breast cancer, initiated or undergone primary breast cancer treatment, and were registered members of Amazona were invited via email to participate. The invitation email included information about the workshop, the first version of the survey questionnaire (to gather feedback for the next phase of the study), and a consent form.

Participants were stratified based on age into two groups: i) above 60 and ii) 60 and below. This stratification assumed that younger individuals might be more adept at adopting new technology and that the groups would therefore have different user needs and preferences.

3.2 Focused discussions and workshops with medical experts

An online workshop was held in July 2021 with members from most consortium partners, including all three clinical partners (INCLIVA, SUH, RSTO) and all technical teams, to define the system functionalities required for clinical trials. These discussions will continue throughout the project to ensure alignment with clinical needs. The workshop covered the following key goals:

- Configuration and structure of clinical trials in the REBECCA system
- Measurement instruments and their relation to the REBECCA Information Model
- The questionnaires to be answered through the mobile app
- The dashboard data views
- Exporting data sets for further analysis
- Open questions regarding deployment and data access

The narrative scenarios created for the focus groups were also utilized in this meeting to identify key use cases of the REBECCA system in clinical practice and research. One additional narrative scenario was specifically designed to describe how the system will be used by the doctors and researchers. This scenario covered aspects such as system organization (adding BCPs, mapping studies, and CRF functionalities), design choices (data input methods, cloud-based or distributed systems), and data presentation (views, levels of detail, and comparisons between individual BCPs and population statistics). High-fidelity mock-ups and wireframes supported these discussions.

Additional details and outcomes of these decisions will be documented in Deliverable D1.4.

3.3 Large-scale questionnaire survey

The survey was conducted in August 2021 and aimed to gather data on user needs and preferences. The questionnaire was electronically distributed to both BCP and BCS.

Women of all ages who have been diagnosed with breast cancer and have initiated or completed primary breast cancer treatment were invited to participate in the survey. An invitation email containing information about the study and a link to the questionnaire will be sent to five breast cancer societies (Amazona, BCF Rosa Gotland, BCF Maria, BCF Moa-Lina, and Ung Cancer) in Sweden to distribute it online to their members.

The questionnaire shared (Annex B.1), was a revised version of the questionnaire discussed in the co-creation workshop and was developed and administered using REDCap. It included a mix of single-choice, multiple-choice, and ranking questions, and covered multiple topics, such as demographic information, internet usage, eHealth tools, social media, and preferences related to smartphone apps, smartwatches, and companion apps. It was available in both Swedish and English. The Swedish version (Figure 5) underwent review by a group of native Swedish-speaking BCP to ensure clarity and relevance.

Projekt REBECCA - Frågeformulär för användarkrav [SWÉ]

Följande frågeformulär syftar till att identifiera behoven och kraven hos bröstcancerpatienter för REBECCA-applikationen. REBECCA-systemet består av patientens mobilapp och en möjlig tvärande mobilapp + en annan applikation eller annan digitaltjänst som är integrerad med systemet för att registrera vikt, tryck, smärtmått och andra tekniska data från patientens mobilapp. REBECCA-systemet kommer att kunna ge feedback i tekniska data tillbaka till användare och personal på sjukhus. Detta med förhoppningen att kunna optimera behandling, smärtbehandling och bemötande av patienter efter avslutad primärbehandling t.ex. ytterligare möjlighet att träffa läkare eller sjukvårdare, bättre information under sjukvårdsprocessen, m.m.

Information om dig som deltagare De första frågorna handlar om dig. Vi kommer bara att använda denna information för att säkerställa att alla underslagor av bröstcancerpatienter är lika representerade när vi utformar REBECCA-systemet. Dessa frågor kommer inte att användas för att påverka hur REBECCA integreras i klinisk praxis. Informationen du tillhandahåller är helt anonym och kommer inte att användas till något annat syfte.

Generell information

Hur gammal är du (år)?

Vilken är din högsta avslutade utbildning?

Vad är din relationstatus?

Vad är din anställningsstatus?

I vilket land är du bosatt?

Kämnad/erfarenhet av viss teknologi Det här avsnittet innehåller frågor om hur bekant och erfaren du är med att använda viss teknologi. Det syftar till att hjälpa oss att förstå bröstcancerpatienters behov och för att bättre utforma och anpassa REBECCA-systemet till din livsstil och dina behov.

Hur ofta använder du internet?

Vilka olika enheter använder du för att komma ut på nätet?

Vilken webbläsare använder du på din telefon?

Vilka andra webbläsare använder du med din telefon?

Vilken webbläsare använder du på din Android-laptop/PC?

Vilken webbläsare använder du med din Android-laptop/PC, Microsoft Windows eller Apple?

Vilka är de viktigaste frågorna, vilka av dessa faktorer har påverkat användet av bröstcancer- och bröstcancerbehandlingen?

1: Inte alls
2: Lite
3: Lite påverkan
4: Påverkan
5: Påverkan
6: Påverkan
7: Påverkan
8: Påverkan
9: Påverkan

1: Ingen användning
2: Lite användning
3: Lite användning
4: Påverkan
5: Påverkan
6: Påverkan
7: Påverkan
8: Påverkan
9: Påverkan

Figure 5. Large scale survey

3.4 Co-creation meetings to develop behavioural indicators

Three co-creation meetings are designed to bring together clinical and technical partners to collaboratively develop behavioural indicators for cancer-related fatigue, osteopenia/osteoporosis and peripheral neuropathy. The meetings, held online between each clinical site and AUTH, focusing on identifying and addressing the specific needs related to the health conditions assigned to each clinical site.

The meeting with INCLIVA in November 2021 and with SUH in December 2021 gathered insights on relevant indicators to osteopenia/osteoporosis and treatment-induced fatigue. The upcoming meeting at RSTO in March 2022 will address the relevant indicators to peripheral neuropathy. These meetings are essential for ensuring continuous input from all partners throughout the project's duration, especially after each major system's release.

3.5 Preliminary use of the system – Pilot testing

A pilot testing is planned for spring 2022 and will be designed to provide insights into the app's usability, user experience, and functionality, as well as to identify areas for improvement before broader implementation.

This pilot will aim to evaluate the proposed app and compare its usage among participants between the first and second week of testing. The testing will follow a single-centre pilot design, consisting of an initial information meeting, a supervised pilot-test of the app, a follow-up meeting, and an unsupervised pilot-test of the app (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Study design

Inclusion criteria for participation will comprise women aged 18 years or older, able to speak and read Swedish, having completed their primary breast cancer treatment within the previous 10 years (self-reported), owning an Android or iOS smartphone, and having daily access to the internet. Exclusion criteria will include current cancer recurrence or the presence of medical conditions (e.g., dementia, anorexia) that might independently affect app usage. All participants will receive comprehensive

information about the study and will provide written informed consent prior to participating.

Participants will attend an informational meeting in small groups to receive detailed guidance on study procedures and app usage. During the meeting, participants will provide written consent before gaining access to the app. Throughout the supervised one-week period, participants will use the app under guided conditions with support from researchers. Following this, a second week will allow participants to use the app freely without any guidance.

A feedback questionnaire will be developed and distributed to participants during the follow-up meeting. The questionnaire will include a mix of standardized items and open-ended questions to gather user feedback on the app's usability and functionality.

3.6 Development of individualized consultation protocol and reporting scheme

To support the goal of enhancing follow-up care and QoL of BCS, KI will develop a comprehensive advisory guide to serve as a practical tool for all clinical sites, ensuring consistent and personalized lifestyle counselling for patients during intervention studies.

The guide will be based on post-cancer lifestyle guidelines, drawing from international and local resources such as the WHO, WCRF, and CDC. These guidelines will be synthesized across key lifestyle areas (e.g. diet, physical activity, sleep, alcohol use, etc.) and tailored to REBECCA's real-world data indicators.

Before its finalization, the advisory guide will be shared with all project partners for feedback, suggestions, and collaborative input. The finalized advisory guide will present these recommendations in a standardized, user-friendly format, offering practical examples to address patient challenges based on collected data from the REBECCA system.

3.7 Continuous co-creation and user feedback integration

Co-creation activities will be a cornerstone of the project's development, ensuring a user-centred approach. Amazona established a dedicated testing group to evaluate the pApp and cApp, provide detailed feedback, identify bugs, and foster collaboration. Regular weekly meetings between the technical team and Amazona will ensure seamless engagement, with a focus on planning, monitoring progress, and refining system functionalities to align with user needs and project goals.

3.8 Validation of the system

A validation of the system is planned for spring 2023 to ensure the patient app's reliability and suitability for its intended purpose. The aim will be to evaluate the app's ability to accurately collect and analyse real-world data related to lifestyle factors, ensuring its effectiveness as a tool for personalized patient counselling. The specific methodology for validation will be decided at a later stage, based on emerging needs and the aspects that require further testing.

4 Updates and additions to co-creation activities at M39

4.1 Overview of co-creation activities

This section presents the updates made to the co-creation activities up to M39, compared to the initial planning at M9. It includes an overview (Table 1) of the originally planned activities, the activities planned but not initially defined in detail (marked with * in Table 1) and the additional ones introduced (marked with bold in Table 1) during the project's progression.

Table 1. Co-Creation Activities (M9–M39)

Date	Month	Activity
June 2021	M3	Co-creation workshop / Focus groups
July 2021	M4	Workshop with medical experts
August 2021	M5	Large-scale survey
November 2021	M8	Osteopenia / Osteoporosis meeting (INCLIVA)
December 2021	M9	Treatment-Induced Fatigue (SUH)
<i>Activities after M9</i>		
March 2022	M12	Peripheral Neuropathy (RSTO)
May 2022	M14	Pilot testing
<i>January - April 2023*</i>	M22-M25	<i>cApp co-creation</i>
March 2023	M24	Norwegian Cancer Society meeting
May 2023	M26	Individualized consultation protocol
<i>June 2023*</i>	<i>M27</i>	<i>Validation study</i>
November 2023	M32	Positive reporting categories into the pApp
April 2024	M37	Feasibility study

*Activities planned in M9 but not predefined in its approach and methodology

Following the table, this section describes the methodology of the three new co-creation activities, along with the validation study and the cApp co-creation, both of which were planned in M9 but not initially defined in detail. The validation study was conducted to assess key aspects of system performance, while the cApp co-creation followed an iterative approach to finalize user requirements. The newly introduced activities (the Norwegian Cancer Society meeting, the integration of positive event reporting categories into the pApp, and the feasibility study) were designed to strengthen system validation, enhance user engagement, and refine the REBECCA system based on patient and expert feedback. A comprehensive presentation of the results from all activities described in this deliverable can be found in D1.4.

4.2 Companion App co-creation

To finalize the cApp, an iterative co-creation process was conducted, integrating feedback from clinical experts, patients, and consortium members. Initially, from January to February 2023, clinical experts (including doctors, researchers, and study nurses) were asked to provide input on the in-app questions via Teamwork. These questions aimed to capture patients' behaviour and QoL from the perspective of their companions as external observers. Subsequently, in March and April 2023, workshop activities were organized by Amazona, AUTH, and KI, engaging a focus group of six BCS members. Two iterative workshops were held to refine the cApp's content and functionality, ensuring it aligned with user needs and clinical requirements.

4.3 Norwegian Cancer Society meeting

On March 21, 2023, the Norwegian Cancer Society organized a meeting with 30 of its members to discuss the ongoing REBECCA study at SUH. The meeting aimed to present the project's objectives and gather feedback and provided valuable insights, reaffirming the critical role of the REBECCA project in addressing unmet needs in post-cancer care.

4.4 Validation study

The aim of this validation study was to evaluate the functionality and accuracy of the GPS in identifying Point of Interest (POIs), ensure proper data collection through the app and wearable devices, and gather feedback from participants to refine the process and address potential issues before conducting the intervention studies. The study protocol can be found in Annex C.

Respondents who agreed to participate in the study were invited in groups of 4 to 6 people, for a 3-hour activity. Four sessions were held, one in the morning 09:00 -12:00 and three in the evening 16:30-19:30. The validation study was conducted for three days during the week 19-22 of June 2023.

The study was divided into three parts: an indoor session, an outdoor activity, and a final indoor session. It began at the Amazona head office in Stockholm, where participants were briefed on the study, trained to use an app and smartwatches, and completed a health questionnaire. The outdoor activity included a meal at a restaurant, where participants photographed their food and drink, followed by a brief stop at a shopping mall. Afterward, they returned to the office, provided feedback, and removed the watches (Figure 7).

Figure 7. Study protocol

4.5 Positive reporting categories into the pApp

A dedicated co-creation meeting was held with the participation of four Amazona volunteers, for integrating positive life events reporting into the pApp. This initiative builds on initial patient feedback from SUH, INCLIVA, and Amazona volunteers during the previous reporting period, where participants expressed a desire to report positive life events through the app.

In response to this feedback, in September 2023 KI attempted to create positive categories for integration into the pApp. KI researchers convened a brainstorming session with 10 women from their research group to identify meaningful events that could enhance the app by better reflecting the positive and significant aspects of daily life for BCS. This process generated an extensive initial list of events, which was subsequently organized into broader domains. The list was further refined with input from consortium partners and finalized during in-depth discussions with Amazona

representatives in November 2023. The process of developing the annotation categories is depicted in Figure 8.

Figure 8. Process of creating positive reporting categories into the pApp.

4.6 Feasibility study

The REBECCA-KI-Feas-QoL study aims to evaluate BCS acceptance, engagement, and usage of the REBECCA system in real-world implementation, and it is conducted in the context of Task 6.1. The secondary aim of the study includes assessing QoL improvements through personalized lifestyle consultations. Over a 3-month monitoring period, the study gathers data via the REBECCA app, wearable devices and self-reports through the app, tracking participants' physical activity, diet, emotional well-being, and internet history.

The study, which began in April 2024 and will conclude in January 2025, is designed to run in two rounds with the goal of reaching 50 participants. The first round began on April 8 and will be completed in September 2024, and the second round will begin on August 26 and the data collection is expected to conclude by the end of November.

Participants attend a baseline meeting at the start of the study, followed by a mid-point personalized consultation (in-person or remote), and an exit meeting at the study's conclusion. Personalized lifestyle consultations are conducted midway through the study, informed by continuous data monitoring.

Figure 9 presents the outline of the feasibility study.

Figure 9. Feasibility study design

5 Conclusions

In conclusion, the REBECCA project adopts a robust evaluation framework and tools as a foundation for its development process. This framework informs and guides the co-creation activities, ensuring they align with the system's objectives and user needs. The co-creation activities outlined in this document, both completed and planned, are integral to the system's evolution, fostering collaboration with patients, healthcare professionals, and other stakeholders. This approach will enhance the system's effectiveness in supporting cancer care and clinical research, ultimately improving follow-up care and QoL for BCS.

A. ANNEX A: Focus groups

A.1 Focus group discussion guide

Topics	Questions
Experience using smartphones, smartwatches, and wearables	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is your experience using smartphones? • How often do you use your smartphones? • Do you download applications in your smartphones? • What is your experience using smartwatches and wearables? • Do you like it? If yes, why? If not, why?
Opinions on the companion app	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you think about the companion app? • Would you like to use it? If yes, why? If not, why? • Who would you like to be your companion?
Opinions on sharing personal information and what is acceptable to monitor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is okay to monitor/record? • Is there information you are not comfortable sharing with doctors/nurses? For example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Are you comfortable sharing how you move daily? ○ Are you comfortable sharing your online behaviour if it could indicate anxiety or depression?
Description of a good and bad day	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What characterizes a good / bad day for you?
Opinion on the value of using a system like REBECCA	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can you see any other value or benefit in using a system/app like REBECCA? • How do you think REBECCA can change today's treatment after completion of primary care? • What can the doctors/nurses learn from the data that REBECCA collects? For example: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Can the information about physical activity improve the interaction/meeting with the doctor/nurse? ○ Could a weekly mood questionnaire improve the interaction/meeting with the doctor/nurse?

Questions to improve the questionnaire	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Were the questions relevant?• Were there any questions that could be perceived as offensive/negative?• Were the questions understandable?• How was the length of the questionnaire?• How much time do you think is acceptable/appropriate to answer a questionnaire?
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B. ANNEX B: Large scale survey

B.1 User Requirements Questionnaire [EN]

The following questionnaire is aimed at identifying the needs and requirements of breast cancer patients (BCPs) for the REBECCA project.

The REBECCA system (patient mobile app + companion mobile app + wearable) is envisioned as a system to monitor different lifestyle, emotional and online behavioural aspects of the breast cancer patients. The system will also be able to provide some feedback/historical data back to the patient, as well as to the supervising health professionals, in order to optimize treatment, care and management of patients after the completion of primary treatment (e.g., additional opportunity to see a doctor or nurse, better information during doctor's visits and follow-up meetings, etc.).

Information about you as a participant

The first questions are about you. We will only use this information to make sure that all subgroups of breast cancer patients are equally represented when we design the REBECCA system. These questions will not be used to influence how REBECCA is integrated into clinical practice. The information you provide is completely anonymous and will not be used for any other purpose.

General information

- Single choice questions
 - Multiple choice questions
-
1. How old are you (years)?
 - Under 30
 - 30 - 35
 - 36 - 40
 - 41 - 45
 - 46 - 50
 - 51 - 55
 - 56 - 60
 - 61 - 65
 - 66 - 70
 - 71 - 75
 - Over 75
 2. What is the highest level of education you have completed?
 - None

- Primary school
 - Secondary school
 - Bachelor's degree
 - Master's degree
 - Doctoral degree
 - I prefer not to answer
3. What is your relationship status?
- Single, never married
 - Married, cohabiting or in a relationship
 - Widowed
 - Divorced / Separated
 - I prefer not to answer
4. What is your employment status?
- Employee / Civil servant
 - Self-employed
 - Unemployed but looking for work
 - Unemployed but not currently looking for work
 - Retired
 - On sick leave
 - On parental leave
 - I prefer not to answer
5. In which country are you resident?

Medical history (since your last diagnosis)
--

6. Is your primary cancer treatment finished?
- Yes
 - No
7. Have you ever had a recurrence of breast cancer?
- Yes
 - No
8. How long ago were you diagnosed with breast cancer?
- 6 months or less
 - 7-12 months
 - 1-2 years
 - 3-5 years
 - 6-10 years
 - More than 10 years
 - I prefer not to answer
9. What type(s) of cancer treatment(s) have you had?

- Surgery without lymph node dissection
 - Surgery with lymph node dissection
 - Mastectomy (total or partial removal of the breast tissue)
 - Radiation therapy
 - Chemotherapy
 - Immunotherapy (a way to make the body's immune system attack cancer cells), such as PD-1 and PD-L1 inhibitors
 - Targeted drug therapies (e.g. hormonal treatment, HER2 treatment, etc.)
 - Breast reconstruction
 - Other treatment
 - I prefer not to answer
10. What kind of treatments are you currently undergoing (if any)?
- No treatment
 - Surgery without lymph node dissection
 - Surgery with lymph node dissection
 - Breast conservation surgery
 - Mastectomy (total or partial removal of the breast tissue)
 - Radiation therapy
 - Chemotherapy
 - Immunotherapy (a way to make the body's the body's immune system to attack cancer cells), such as PD-1 and PD-L1 inhibitors
 - Targeted drug therapies (e.g. hormonal therapy, HER2 treatment, etc.)
 - Other treatment
 - I prefer not to answer
11. In the last month, have you experienced any other health-related problems?
- Fatigue / tiredness
 - Neuropathy (nerve pain in the hands, arms, feet and legs)
 - Bone health problems (osteoporosis) / joint pain
 - Depression
 - Eating disorders
 - Anxiety
 - Neurological disease (e.g. Parkinson's)
 - Other
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me
- What other health-related problems have you experienced in the in the last month?
12. Have you at any time after the primary treatment experienced any other health-related problems?

- Fatigue/tiredness
 - Neuropathy
 - Bone health problems (osteoporosis) / joint pain
 - Depression
 - Eating disorders
 - Anxiety
 - Neurological disease
 - Other
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me
- What other health-related problems have you experienced at any time after the primary treatment?
13. Are you participating in any research / clinical study regarding breast cancer right now, or have you participated in the past?
- I am participating in one or more studies right now
 - I have previously participated in one or more studies
 - I have never participated in any study
 - I prefer not to answer

Familiarity / experience with a particular technology

This section contains questions about how familiar and experienced you are in using certain technologies. It aims to help us understand the needs of breast cancer patients and to better design and adapt the REBECCA System to your lifestyle and needs.

14. How often do you use the internet?

- Daily
- A few times a week
- Once a week
- Rarely
- Never
- I prefer not to answer

15. What different devices do you use to access the internet?

- Android mobile
- iPhone
- Android tablet
- iPad
- Windows laptop or PC
- Apple laptop or PC
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

16. Which browser do you use on your smartphone?

- Google Chrome
- Safari
- Microsoft Edge
- Mozilla Firefox
- Other
- I do not know
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

What other browsers do you use with your phone?

17. Which browser do you use on your android tablet / iPad?

- Google Chrome
- Safari
- Microsoft Edge
- Mozilla Firefox
- Other
- I do not know

- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me
- What other browsers do you use with your android tablet / iPad?
- 18. Which browser do you use on your laptop / PC (Microsoft Windows or Apple)?
 - Google Chrome
 - Safari
 - Microsoft Edge
 - Mozilla Firefox
 - Other
 - I do not know
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me
- What other browsers do you use with your laptop / PC (Microsoft Windows or Apple)?
- 19. What language do you usually use when reading / writing while you are surfing?
 - Swedish
 - English
 - Arabic
 - Spanish
 - Finnish
 - Polish
 - Other language

What other language do you usually use when reading / writing while you are surfing?

Use of social media

- 20. Do you use social media?
 - Yes
 - No
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me
- 21. How do you connect to social media?
 - I use pre-installed apps on my device (phone, tablet, iPad)
 - I use a web browser (either on phone, tablet, iPad, or laptop, MacBook, PC)
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me
- 22. What different social media platforms do you use?
 - Facebook

- Facebook Messenger
 - YouTube
 - Instagram
 - Twitter
 - Reddit
 - Quora
 - Medium
 - LinkedIn
 - WhatsApp
 - Tumblr
 - Pinterest
 - Flickr
 - Viber
 - Snapchat
 - Breast cancer related forums for breast cancer patients
 - Other
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me
- Which different forums for breast cancer patients do you use?
- What other social media do you use?
23. What types of activities do you do via social media in relation to your breast cancer?
- Chatting with friends and other cancer patients
 - Commenting on posts about cancer-related issues
 - Following other cancer patients
 - Posting health updates for family or friends or friends
 - Following patient organizations and associations related to my disease
 - Writing about or posting my own health-related experiences
 - Attending online lectures / online events related to cancer
 - Providing support to other breast cancer patients, either in groups or individually
 - Participating in breast cancer discussion groups
 - Other
 - I do nothing related to my breast cancer diagnosis
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me
 - What other types of activities do you perform via social media that relate to your current health status?

Use of the internet

24. Where do you search for medical information online?

- Google (or other search engines)
- Wikipedia
- YouTube
- Blogs
- Facebook groups
- Various breast cancer related forums
- 1177.se
- Other
- Cancer-related websites, such as the Cancer Foundation or the Breast Cancer Association
- Medical databases such as PubMed
- I do not seek medical information online
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

Which forums do you visit to look for medical information?

Where else do you look for medical information?

25. Where do you seek support and other social interactions online?

- Facebook
- Facebook Messenger
- YouTube
- Instagram
- Twitter
- Reddit
- Quora
- Medium
- LinkedIn
- WhatsApp
- Tumblr
- Pinterest
- Flickr
- Viber
- Snapchat
- Various breast cancer related forums
- Other
- I prefer not to answer

This is not relevant for me

What specific forums do you use to get support and other social interactions online?

Where else do you seek support and other social interactions online?

Online activities

26. What kind of activities do you do online in relation to your breast cancer?

- Participating in virtual forums and events related to cancer
- Reading about other breast cancer patients' experiences
- Watching videos and the like related to cancer
- Writing a diary or running a blog
- Searching for medical cancer-related information
- Attending training courses related to cancer
- Psychotherapeutic techniques to deal with anxiety
- Looking for ways to deal with emotional crisis and depression
- Searches related to psychosocial problems and how to improve my mood
- Participating in discussion forums related to cancer
- Searching for newly available treatments
- Providing support to other breast cancer patients, either in groups or individually
- Searching for ongoing clinical trials for cancer
- Searching for job opportunities and/or financial support for cancer survivors
- Other
- None of the above
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

What other types of activities do you perform online in relation to your current health status?

27. How do you express your thoughts and concerns online or via social media?

- I make posts via my profile to describe my concerns and problems
- I share videos where I express how I feel
- I only comment in private groups and forums about how I deal with my worries and problems
- I join specific forums to express my anxiety and concerns
- I use emojis to express how I feel
- I share other people's stories about cancer to express what I feel
- Other

- I don't make posts or comments about how I feel
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

In what other ways do you express your thoughts and problems online or via social media?

28. How often do you use the above ways to express your thoughts, concerns and problems?
- Never
 - Daily
 - Weekly
 - When I feel anxious or depressed
 - Other
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me

How often do you use the above ways to express your thoughts, worries and problems? Please specify:

29. Do you use (or have you used) any apps related to breast cancer?
- I am currently using such an app
 - I have used such an app in the past
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me

What type of app related to cancer have you used so far?

30. Have you ever used a smartwatch or other activity bracelet?
- Yes
 - No
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me

31. What type of smartwatch / activity bracelet have you used?
- Fitbit (e.g. Charge, Versa, Sense)
 - Garmin (e.g. Venu, Vivoactive)
 - Apple Watch
 - WearOS (Android) watch (e.g., Samsung Galaxy Watch,
 - Huawei Watch)
 - Other

What type of smartwatch / activity wristband have you used? Specify brand or type.

32. Some systems (such as Google) allow you to export parts of your personal data (for example browsing history). This process usually requires a few clicks. How willing would you be to perform such a procedure (with the help of a detailed guide) every one or two months in order to provide the exported data for analysis by the REBECCA system?

I would never do that ----- I can easily do that

Overall questions about the REBECCA system and participation

The following questions will help us to prioritize which aspects of behaviour to focus on during the development of the REBECCA system.

Lifestyle questions

How important are the following factors to your quality of life after completing primary breast cancer treatment?

1: Not important

7: Very important

Leave it blank if it is not relevant.

33. Physical activity level (e.g., number of steps per day, number of exercise sessions, duration and intensity)
34. Dietary and nutritional habits (e.g., number of meals, snacks, time of day, irregular eating, type of food, home meals vs. restaurants vs. fast food)
35. Smoking (e.g., frequency, quantity)
36. Personal transportation (e.g., being mobile at home, ability to make leisure trips and visits to places outside the local area, performing social leisure activities such as going to reading clubs or similar)
37. Being able to spend time at home, enjoying time with pets or other quiet hobbies
38. Work (e.g., working vs. not working, working from home or office, commuting method, sick leave)
39. Social interaction, relationships with family members and friends
40. Sex drive
41. Online activities, breast cancer related activity (e.g., internet searches, online discussions, social media, various forums)

Based on the previous question, which of these factors have been significantly affected by breast cancer and breast cancer treatment?

1: not at all

7: great impact

Leave it blank if it is not relevant.

42. Physical activity level (e.g., number of steps per day, number of exercise sessions, duration and intensity)
43. Dietary and nutritional habits (e.g., number of meals, snacks, time of day, irregular eating, type of food, home meals vs. restaurants vs. fast food)
44. Smoking (e.g., frequency, quantity)
45. Personal transportation (e.g., being mobile at home, ability to make leisure trips and visits to places outside the local area, performing social leisure activities such as going to reading clubs or similar)
46. Being able to spend time at home, enjoying time with pets or other quiet hobbies
47. Work (e.g., working vs. not working, working from home or office, commuting method, sick leave)
48. Social interaction, relationships with family members and friends
49. Sex drive
50. Online activities, breast cancer related activity (e.g., internet searches, online discussions, social media, various forums)

Privacy

This section contains issues relevant to user privacy, data control, access and use.

1: Not at all

7: Very comfortable

51. How comfortable are you with sharing your (GPS) location with the REBECCA system?

- Please note that location will only be used to derive information such as how much time you spend at home, how often you go on outings, etc., in order to enable the REBECCA system to better estimate your mood and behaviour.

I would never share my location -----I'm totally okay with sharing my location

(Place a mark on the scale above)

52. Similar to the previous question, how comfortable do you feel with sharing specific locations, e.g. home address, work address?

- Please note that this information will only be used in the same way as location information. Please also note that this information will never be transmitted (not even to the REBECCA servers); This information remains only on your phone.

I would never share this address -----I'm totally okay with sharing this address

(Place a mark on the scale above)

In order for the REBECCA system to better understand and estimate your behaviour, it would be beneficial (for the system) if you answered a set of questions at the beginning of the use of the system (e.g. after installing the smartphone application for the first time).

How comfortable are you with answering questions about:

1: Not at all

7: Very comfortable

53. your smoking habits? (Leave it blank if it is not relevant)

54. your drinking habits? (Leave it blank if it is not relevant)

55. your sleeping habits?

View on the information collected by the REBECCA system

This section contains questions related to the information and / or feedback that you would like to receive from the REBECCA system while you use it. Most of this (if not all) will be available to you via the smartphone application.

56. Do you want the REBECCA system to give you feedback on the information collected?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

57. How detailed would you like the information to be?

- Daily reports
- Weekly reports
- Monthly reports
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

58. How often would you like the information to be available?

- Every day
- Every week
- Every month
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

59. How do you prefer the information to be available?

- Non-interactive (e.g., ready-made complete reports)
- Interactive in the app or via a website (e.g., with the possibility to filter information, be able to customize the scope of the report, etc.).

- I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me
60. Do you prefer to rate the reports of the REBECCA system (e.g., mark them as correct or incorrect)?
- Yes
 - No
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me
61. Would you also like to have access to this information via a web interface (e.g. in a web browser such as Google Chrome or Safari from your laptop / PC)?
- Yes
 - No
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant to me
62. Would you like to be able to report specific events / incidents (such as you had a particularly nice day or a hard / stressful day or a difficult / stressful morning / afternoon) using the smartphone application?
- The reporting of such events / incidents would help the REBECCA system to understand changes in behaviour and mental state.
- Yes
 - No
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me
63. How detailed would you like the reporting to be?
- Overall (from good to bad)
 - Possibility to add free text
 - Possibility to add location
 - Possibility to add photos
 - I prefer not to answer
 - This is not relevant for me

Questions about the smartphone application

The smartphone application will periodically ask you to answer certain questions that have been pre-determined by a doctor. Upcoming questions are relevant to that function.

64. How important is it to receive feedback about your lifestyle and behaviour?

Not important at all-----Very important
(Place a mark on the scale above)

65. What lifestyle factors and behaviours do you consider to be important to get feedback on?

- Physical activity
- Diet
- Drinking
- Smoking
- Sleep
- Work
- Travelling
- Other
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me
- What other lifestyle aspects and behaviours do you consider important to receive feedback on?

66. Would you like to be able to permanently reject certain types of questions?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

67. How often would you be comfortable responding to questions? (Choose the option you feel comfortable with)

- Daily
- Every 2-3 days
- Once a week
- Once a month
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

68. How many questions would you be comfortable to answer each time? (Select the maximum number of questions you feel comfortable with)

- 1

- 2 - 3
- 4 - 6
- 6 - 10
- 11 - 15
- 15 - 20
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

Smartwatches and other activity bracelets

This section contains questions about the smartwatches or other activity bracelets that will be part of the patient version of the app. At the moment, it is planned that this activity bracelet will be similar to a fitness band placed around the wrist.

69. How important is it to you that the activity bracelet is small and discreet?

Not important at all-----Very important

(Place a mark on the scale above)

70. How important is it to you that the activity tracker is comfortable (e.g. lightweight, high-quality materials)?

Not important at all-----Very important

(Place a mark on the scale above)

71. How comfortable are you with sleeping with an activity tracker?

Not important at all-----Very important

(Place a mark on the scale above)

72. How often do you think it is acceptable for the activity tracker to require charging?

(Please respond with the most frequent interval that is acceptable)

- Every day
- Every other day
- Every 3-4 days
- Every 5-7 days
- Once a week
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

73. How long would you be comfortable wearing the wristband before you would want to take it off?

(Select the maximum duration you feel comfortable)

- Up to one hour
- 1-3 hours
- 3-8 hours
- All day (awake time, 12 h)
- All day and night (24 hour, except the time the device needs to be charged)
- I prefer not to answer

- This is not relevant for me

74. How experienced are you in using a wearable device such as a smartwatch (e.g., Android WearOS, Apple watch, Samsung smartwatch) or an activity bracelet (e.g., Fitbit Versa/Charge, Garmin band)?

Never used-----

It is part of my daily routine

(Place a mark on the scale above)

If you are used to using a smartwatch or other activity bracelet, which features are important to you?

1: completely unimportant

7: very important

Leave it blank if it is not relevant.

75. Information on physical activity such as number of steps, calories, altitude

76. Gym and training sessions

77. Heart rate monitoring

78. Sleep monitoring

79. View and / respond to messages from your phone

Companion app

The Companion app is an optional component of the REBECCA system. It is a smartphone application that can be used by a selected partner of the breast cancer patient (e.g., life partner, siblings, friends) to provide additional information about the patient. The purpose is to obtain an external image of the breast cancer patient.

80. Would you like to know what kind of questions are asked in the Companion app?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

81. Would you like the option to opt out of certain questions?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant to me

82. Would you like to know what your selected companion answers?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

83. Would you rely on your companion to decide which questions are relevant to answer?

- Yes
- No
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant to me

The best potential value of the REBECCA system

The Rebecca system aims to support breast cancer patients who have completed their primary treatment in their everyday life and improve their communication with healthcare professionals. This is done by collecting information on patients' daily behaviours such as physical activity, eating habits, sleep and information related to their online behaviours.

84. How long after completion of primary treatment would the REBECCA system have been most useful and important to you?

- Immediately after completion of primary treatment (0 to 6 months)
- 6-12 months after completion of primary treatment
- 12-24 months after completion of primary treatment
- Later than 24 months after completion of
- Primary treatment
- I prefer not to answer
- This is not relevant for me

C. ANNEX C: Validation study protocol

	Actions	Duration
Prepare – Information meeting	Info for the experiment - Sign consent form	30-40 min
	Installation + watches distributed + instructions	
	Fill in Health Questionnaires	15 min
Data collection starts	Walk to the bus stop Hälsingegatan	2 min
Experiment	Take the bus no 53 to the restaurant	11 min (bus ride)
	Go off at Centralen stop	
	Walk to the restaurant Urban Deli https://urbandeli.se/en/sveavagen	11 min
	Eat lunch / dinner	30-40 min
	Walk from the restaurant to the metro station Hötorget	5 min
	Take the metro to Odenplan	4 min (bus ride)
	From Odenplan: Walk to Åhlens	2 min
	Stop: Åhlens 2 participants will enter . 3 participants wait outside	5 min at least
	From Åhlens walk back to Amazonas offices	8 min
	Take off the watches	
Data collection over	Fill in Evaluation Questionnaires	
Prepare for the next day	Give to take home: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Instructions (manually sync, etc.) 2. Chargers for the watches 3. Envelopes 4. Template for the diary 	
TOTAL TIME		Around 3 hours